

PRODUCTION OF PRESENCE:
HISTORICAL LIMITS OF “SENSE-MAKING”

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For a long time, literary and philosophical discourse was dominated by the hermeneutic paradigm. It assumed the universality of text interpretation and identical recipients' reactions to its basic elements. According to this approach, all interactions with the world were viewed through the lens of interpretation and the search of meaning. The relevance of this study is based on the necessity of critically reviewing this assumption. Using H. U. Gumbrecht's theoretical framework, the study examines the idea that the practice of “sense-making” is not an ontological constant, but rather a historically localized phenomenon.

R. Darnton and other literary theorists assumed that there were no differences in readers' reactions to the basic elements of a text, such as semantics, syntax, and tropes [Gumbrecht 1990: 146]. Consequently, they also assumed that the meaning of a text is formed in the same way for all readers. Variation in readings (or individual “concretizations”) arises only because of “voids” in the all-over construction of the text [Gumbrecht 1990: 146].

Nevertheless, according to H. U. Gumbrecht, these general assumptions are not supported by empirical evidence—in practice, different readers react differently to the basic elements of a text [Gumbrecht 1990: 146]. Furthermore, “giving meaning” to phenomena may be a historically localized phenomenon, i.e., it may not be a universal rule of interacting with the things of the world.

H. U. Gumbrecht suggests a challenging question: is the habit of “giving meaning” (or “reading the world”) universal for all people at all ages [Gumbrecht 1990: 146]? For example, there is no reason to believe that Paleolithic people, painting in the Altamira cave, tried to “encrypt” messages as we would do today [Gumbrecht 1990: 146]. And, in the opposite way, we have no valid reason to automatically assume that the world is pre-filled with ready-made meanings.

However, H. U. Gumbrecht suggests studying how meaning is generated and what constitutes an “absence of meaning” [Gumbrecht 1990: 146]. Ultimately, the most important thing is accepting that “giving meaning” is just one of many ways humans interact with the world.

In his book *Production of Presence*, H. U. Gumbrecht states that, during certain historical periods in Europe, particularly during the Middle Ages, “sense-making” was not the dominant mode of interaction with the world [Gumbrecht 2004: 87]. Instead, the experience of presence—direct, unmediated interaction with materialities—was much more important. This does not mean that people did not search for meaning at all, but their perception of the world was more oriented toward the influence of things, their materiality, and the sensations they evoked, rather than their symbolic meaning [Gumbrecht 2004: 80–85].

“Presence” refers to the direct physical impact of things on the human body and senses. In contrast, “meaning” refers to the semantic connections, interpretations, and understandings of messages or symbols. If “meaning” is more related to symbolic, textual, and interpretive spheres, then “presence” is more related to physical, material, and spatial spheres [Gumbrecht 2004: 17].

According to H. U. Gumbrecht, the transition from a culture oriented toward presence, as in the Middle Ages, to a culture oriented toward meaning, as in modernity, is one of the key paradigmatic-historical shifts in Western culture [Gumbrecht 2004: 79]. H. U. Gumbrecht’s theoretical framework aims to bring presence back into focus in the humanities, which have long focused primarily on “sense-making” and interpretation [Gumbrecht 2004: 1].

Concluding the above, it should be noted that the differentiation between the concepts of “meaning” and “presence” proposed by H. U. Gumbrecht is a critical methodological framework for examining the evolution of Western culture. In this context, the central point is that the practice of “sense-making” is not an ontological constant of human existence, but rather a historically localized phenomenon.

While modernity is characterized by a fixation on semantic connections and interpretations, historical retrospectives, particularly those of the Middle Ages, demonstrate an alternative model of interaction that emphasizes the immediate physical impact of phenomena and their materiality. Thus, the aim to bring “presence” back into research discourse is an attempt to challenge the monopoly of interpretation and legitimize physical contact with reality and reality itself as a self-standing phenomenon under study.

References:

1. Gumbrecht, H. U. (1990). The Meaning of Reading. *The Wilson Quarterly*, 14(2). Washington: Woodrow Wilson International Center for Scholars. P. 146. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40258071>
2. Gumbrecht, H. U. (2004). *Production of Presence: What Meaning Cannot Convey*. Stanford: Stanford University Press. 200 p.